

Dear people at Astera,

I am excited to present my postulation for the Astera Open Science Fellowship to work together on the OSOM project detailed below.

I have a professional background in community building, research, and education. I am co-Executive Director of [MetaDocencia](#), a community I was instrumental in growing since our launch in March 2020. MetaDocencia builds scientific and technical capacities in Latin America by co-developing networks, active learning spaces, and accessible resources. With grants from the [Chan Zuckerberg Initiative](#) and [NASA](#), among others, our impact has grown as we gained funding: we have reached an approximate average of 500 researchers per year over almost five years in more than 30 countries on all continents except Antarctica. I have been a tenured researcher for nearly a decade, but I've been doing computational research in molecular biology and teaching at the graduate and post-graduate levels for 20 years. I co-founded [ISCB](#)'s Regional Student Group of Argentina ([RSG-Argentina](#)), where I helped the success of several workshops and annual Symposiums, I co-wrote and co-edited [Vida.exe](#) (Life.exe in English), the first science communication book in Bioinformatics, edited by a major publisher in Spanish. Elected as Secretary of the Argentine Association of Bioinformatics and Computational Biology ([A2B2C](#)), I led the organization of its [first virtual conference in 2021](#) and 25 editions of its [monthly seminars](#), which kept the community together during the pandemic.

I witness isolation as a problem in communication among scientists. Researchers and technicians worldwide increasingly embrace the benefits of communities and shared research environments. However, many barriers still undermine our efforts to connect, mainly the lack of visibility, poor funding, multiple languages, cultural differences, and inadequate incentives. For Open Science (OS) to be truly achievable, it needs to be global and inclusive of every player. Despite many ongoing efforts to catalog the OS practitioners and key resources available, these efforts lack cohesion, usability, and representation.

My solution to this problem is the project "OSOM: an Open Science Ontology and Map." It will develop a new digital asset around the practice of OS, compliant with the [FAIR Principles](#) by design. The map will catalog and help to identify the connections, characteristics, and resources of academic institutions, publishers, funders, and other organizations (such as infrastructure providers, communities of practice, policymakers, etc.) An online website will display the map as an interactive network graph, but it will be released along a text-based, audio-supported, keyboard-navigable accessible version of the data. The project will also build a common, multilingual vocabulary of OS. This will allow any person or organization to communicate without ambiguities, regardless of their localization and language of choice, while enabling programmatic access by computers in a findable and interoperable way. This common vocabulary, consisting of a set of controlled terms around OS and their definitions, organized in a logical, nested manner (usually known as an ontology), allows to reference a resource of any kind always by a recognizable name. These properties, together with **all code and data freely available as CC-BY in an open online repository**, will make the resources remain reusable globally.

My skills are a perfect fit for this job, and I know the right people to fill the gaps in my knowledge. As a computational biologist, I have studied and co-authored peer-reviewed

papers and Python software on protein-protein interaction networks and the development of an ontology for protein experiments. My experience in OS, community building, and the study and description of protein interactions will be crucial for the success of this project. I am hardly an average programmer and designer, which limits the potential of having a usable, interactive, and accessible database to explore. Still, I expect to work side-by-side with an experienced software developer and a creative designer. I am not an expert in statistics, but OSOM can be used to derive much-needed metrics from graph-like networks (such as recognizing the centrality and reciprocity of participants). I encourage you to review Jessica Formoso's proposal, which would perfectly synergize with this project.

Several organizations are developing a map of OS, but none are as global, comprehensive, community-driven, and accessible as OSOM. My connections are numerous but not large enough. We'll ask the global OS community to contribute to OSOM, but I expect to steward the project and provide the blueprints we can further refine. I am eager to work with MetaDocencia's team to capitalize on its expertise and abilities, such as those gained from our previous effort, "[Mapping of Open Science in Latin America](#)." OSOM and its associated data will be populated through an open call to communities, especially to those already working on OS mapping, like [COS](#) and [OpenAIRE](#). Initially, I will recur to MetaDocencia's globally distributed [partners](#), including [OKFN](#), [Access2Perspectives](#), [FORRT](#), [IOI](#), and [OpenLabEC](#), to gather their existing mappings and databases into an all-encompassing, unified resource. They will also assist in defining the ontology terms, synonyms, and translations that will enable a uniquely inclusive, understandable, and usable vocabulary for the map and any OS-related project. **As a remote fellow, I will be delighted to shape this initial idea with others further.**

The Project Milestones per quarter are:

- Q1. A first draft of a comprehensive OS Database and a common vocabulary is presented
- Q2. Community members join and expand the Map and Ontology
- Q3. A first draft of an Interactive Map and Ontology is available
- Q4. A fine-tuned, FAIR Map and Ontology, including metrics, is released

The Project Budget (hidden)

Thank you very much for taking the time to review my application. I am confident that my project will advance Astera's goals and accomplish a more connected, healthy, and effective OS. I look forward to working together.

Kind regards,

Nicolás Palopoli